

The Correlation of Total IGE, And Complete Blood Count in the Sera of Allergic Rhinitis Patients in Babylon Province, Iraq

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ABSTRACT

Background: Allergic rhinitis (AR) is a common condition that affects the quality of life for sufferers all over the world. AR is a chronic immunoglobulin E-mediated inflammatory condition caused by aeroallergens.

Objectives: The purpose of this research is to investigate the correlation between the clinical severity of allergic rhinitis patients and the levels of total IgE, complete blood count, disease duration, and disease onset among patients.

Methods: In this case-control study, 45 individuals with allergic rhinitis and 45 seemingly healthy controls of both sexes were randomly selected. Both the patient and control groups provided blood samples. To use the ELISA method to estimate the amount of total IgE, the complete blood count (CBC) test was performed automatically.

Results: The study found a statistically significant increase ($P < 0.001$) in total IgE levels in allergic rhinitis serum compared to the control group. The linear regression analysis found a significant positive correlation between IgE and disease onset ($p < 0.002$). There were significant differences between WBC and lymphocytes ($p < 0.02$), neutrophils ($p < 0.000$), and eosinophils with red blood cells ($p < 0.000$). There is a significant negative connection between disease duration and onset ($p < 0.000$).

Conclusion The findings showed that, in comparison to the control group, patients with allergic rhinitis had noticeably higher levels of inflammatory markers. High levels of eosinophils and IgE were indicated of allergic rhinitis, an inflammation of the airways. These linked them to the clinical severity of allergic rhinitis.

Keywords: Allergic Rhinitis, Total IgE, Complete Blood Count.

1. INTRODUCTION

Rhinitis refers to a set of symptoms caused by nasal inflammation and/or mucosal dysfunction [1]. Allergic rhinitis is an inflammation of the nasal mucosal membranes that is followed by a variety of symptoms including nasal mucosa edema, nasal discharge, itching, and others [2]. It is particularly popular among 20 and 44 years [3]. Allergens are proteins found in airborne particles such as dust mites, pollens, molds, insect excrement, and animal dander that cause allergic rhinitis [4]. Allergic rhinitis is defined by the increase of inflammatory cells in the nasal mucosal membrane [5]. Allergic rhinitis allergies are caused by Th-2 lymphocytes, which cause inflammation and produce allergen-specific IgE [6]. Dendritic cells identify allergens, which promotes Th2 cell development and cytokine release. Allergic rhinitis severity is defined as mild, moderate, or severe according to the ARIA guidelines [7]. The ARIA recommendations divide Allergic rhinitis symptoms into intermittent and persistent categories based on the duration of symptoms in patients. In highly developed nations, between 10 to 30

percent of people suffer with allergic rhinitis, while in developing countries, the condition is becoming more common [8]. According to fundamental scientific and epidemiologic evidence, allergic rhinitis is a component of a systemic inflammatory process, which is followed by other mucous membrane inflammatory conditions as asthma, rhinosinusitis, and allergic conjunctivitis [9]. Despite the complexity of the mechanism underlying allergic rhinitis, IgE has been shown to be a key mediator of allergic rhinitis in the pathogenesis and aggravation of allergies [10]. However, the age and gender of patients may have an impact on the serum level of IgE. Therefore, the goal of this study is to evaluate the link between the clinical severity of allergic rhinitis patients and the levels of total IgE, complete blood count, disease duration, and the onset of the among patients.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Subjects study

Forty-five allergic rhinitis patients were collected, from October 2025 to March 2025, these individuals had allergic rhinitis at the Specialized Center of Allergy in Babylon city, Iraq, including 32 males and 13 females with age range of (34.6 ± 2.5) year. The patients were clinically examined and diagnosed by the consultant medical staff. The diagnosis of allergic rhinitis was based on the guidelines of ARIA [11]. The inclusion criteria for allergic rhinitis were symptoms of nasal obstruction, rhinorrhea, sneezing and nasal pruritus. Forty-five of healthy people as a control, including 30 females and 15 males with ages ranging from (34.3 ± 6.4) years.

2.2. Total IgE level

Serum IgE Kit (Elabscience / USA) was used for detection of total IgE level using enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) technique.

2.3. Complete blood count

The Beckman Coulter Analyzer (Beckman, Germany) was used for CBC test.

3. Testing Methods

3.1. Hematological Test

Total and differential counts of White blood cell (WBC) was detected using CBC test automatically.

3.2. Determination of Total IGE Serum Level

A total of 5 mL of blood was taken via vein puncture and stored in a gel tube for serum after centrifugation at 6,000 rpm for 15 minutes. The serum was kept at -20°C . The level of Total IgE was assessed in sera of allergic rhinitis patients and controls by means of ELISA (, using a kit from (Elabscience / USA). Serum IgE concentrations were expressed in ng/ml.

3.3. Statistics Analytical:

Data were analyzed using SPSS 20 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, version 20). Results were reported as means and standard deviations. Associations between categorical variables were assessed with the chi-square test, and differences between two group means were determined using the independent t-test. Statistical significance was set at $P \leq 0.05$.

3.4. Ethical considerations:

The study was carried out with ethical permission in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Patients provided analytical and verbal consent, and consent forms were reviewed and approved. In October 2025, a local ethics commission will act in accordance with document 432A.

4. RESULTS:

4.1. Demographical Study

The study included 45 patients (mean age 34.6 ± 2.5 years) were diagnosed with allergic rhinitis by dermatologist and 45 healthy controls (mean age 34.3 ± 6.4 years). The case group consisted of 13 females (28.9%) and 32 males (71.1%). Table 1 shows a comparison of the patients' clinical and demographic features to those of the controls.

Table 1: Demographic study for allergic rhinitis groups and control

Variables	Category	Patient (n=45)	Control (n=45)	p-value
		No. (%) or Mean \pm S. D		
Mean of Age		34.6 \pm 2.5	34.3 \pm 6.4	0.909(NS)
Sex	Male	32 (71.1%)	30 (66.7%)	0.820(NS)
	Female	13 (28.9%)	15 (33.3%)	
Age (year)	≥ 20	4 (8.9%)	4 (8.9%)	0.974(NS)
	21-40	27 (60%)	26 (57.8%)	
	>40	14 (31.1%)	15 (33.3%)	
BMI	18.5-24.9	13 (28.9%)	14 (31.1%)	0.067(NS)
	25-29.9	17 (37.8%)	25 (55.6%)	
	≥ 30	15 (33.3%)	6 (13.3%)	
Family history	Yes	25 (55.5%)	-	0.456(NS)
	No	20 (44.4%)	-	
Education	Primary	18 (40%)	8 (17.8%)	0.006**(HS)
	Secondary	17 (37.8%)	13 (28.9%)	
	College	10 (22.2%)	24 (53.3%)	
Smoking	Non-smoker	36 (80%)	28 (62.2%)	0.063(NS)
	Smoker	9 (20%)	17 (37.8%)	
Duration (year)	<1	2 (4.4%)	-	0.003**(HS)
	1-5	16 (35.6%)		
	6-10	9 (20%)		
	>10	18 (40%)		
Severity of symptoms	Sever	25 (55.6%)	-	0.0001**(HS)
	Moderate	19 (42.2%)		
	Mild	1(2.2%)		

NS: Non-significant, HS: High significant.

According to the Demographic study, the data presented in Table (1) show that males 32 (71.1%) have a higher percentage of gender than female 13 (28.9%). With regard to age, the age of allergic rhinitis patients and control ranged from (13-50) year, with no significant difference was observed between the four age categories. With regard to BMI, Family history, and smoking, no significant difference was observed between control and patients' groups.

While there are higher significant differences between control and patients' groups in education. Regarding duration and severity of symptoms there are higher significant differences with allergic rhinitis.

The onset age had a higher percentage 44.4% in the age range of between 5 and 20 years, followed by the age range 21-35 at 40%, and the lowest percentage was 15.6% in the age range 36-50 years, Figure 1.

Figure 1: Distribution of allergic rhinitis according to onset of age.

4.2. Hematological results

There were significant variations in total and differential WBC, monocytes and lymphocytes between the case and control groups. Furthermore, Neutrophils and Eosinophils showed substantial differences. The present investigation found no significant differences between patients and controls in terms of basophils and RBC counts as shown in Table (2).

Table 2: WBCs count in allergic rhinitis patients and control group

Parameters	Patients (45)	Control (45)	p-value
	Mean±S.D		
WBC x10 ³ /μL	8.31±2.1	7.27±2.0	0.019* (S)
Lym x10 ³ /μL	2.75±0.5	2.48±0.6	0.040*(S)
Mon x10 ³ /μL	2.46±0.4	1.76±0.7	0.016* (S)
Neu x10 ³ /μL	46.03±7.2	52.37±9.9	0.008**(HS)
Eso x10 ³ /μL	0.35±0.01	0.14±0.02	0.0001**(HS)
Bas x10 ³ /μL	0.46±0.01	0.43±0.02	0.593 (NS)
RBC x10 ⁶ /μL	4.74±0.6	4.73±0.5	0.913(NS)

Data are expressed as mean ± standard deviation. Independent sample t-test was used
-NS: Non-significant, HS: High significant, S: Significant

4.3. Total IGE level

Figure 2 shows a significant difference in Total IgE levels between patients and controls (P-value ≤ 0.01), with 12.3 ± 6.07 vs 8.7 ± 4.91 ng/ml, respectively.

Figure 2: Mean difference in concentration of IgE (ng/ml) between controls and allergic rhinitis patients. *** indicates high significant.

4.4. Relationship between IGE and differential WBCs counts in allergic rhinitis patients

Table 5 revealed a significant positive connection between IgE and disease onset ($p < 0.002$). Furthermore, between WBC with both lymphocytes ($p < 0.029$) and neutrophils ($p < 0.000$), as well as Eosinophil with RBC ($p < 0.000$). While a significant negative correlation between disease duration and onset ($p < 0.000$).

Table (5): The correlation serum level IgE, CBC, duration and onset of allergic rhinitis

		Onset	IgE	WBC	Lym	Mon	Neu	Eso	Bas	RBC
Duration	r	-.544**	.032	.120	.037	.075	.231	-.160	.032	-.207
	Sig.	.000	.836	.431	.808	.624	.126	.295	.833	.173
Onset	r	1	.445**	-.125	.037	-.062	-.255	.235	.115	.205
	Sig.		.002	.412	.810	.685	.091	.120	.453	.176
IgE	r		1	-.273	-.048	-.105	-.199	-.128	.050	-.016
	Sig.			.069	.753	.494	.190	.402	.746	.917
WBC	r			1	.326*	.223	.865**	.008	-.237	-.074
	Sig.				.029	.140	.000	.960	.117	.630
Lym	r				1	.132	-.041	.169	-.088	.043
	Sig.					.387	.789	.267	.565	.781
Mon	r					1	.204	-.082	.204	-.070
	Sig.						.180	.591	.180	.646
Neu	r						1	-.364*	-.203	-.280
	Sig.							.014	.182	.063
Eso	r							1	.019	.571**
	Sig.								.903	.000
Bas	r								1	-.120
	Sig.									.432

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

5. Discussion:

Based on research, allergic rhinitis is reported to peak in the second to fourth decades of life before gradually reducing, [12]. According to the results of this study, allergic rhinitis was present in individuals aged 13 to 50 years, with the 21- to 40-year-old age group being the most frequent, and more prevalent in males than in females. Previously, comparable data were published, and the highest prevalence was recorded among allergic rhinitis patients between the ages of 20 and 44 [3]. However, it is a widely frequent condition that affects people of all ages, peaking during puberty [13]. Researchers have observed that allergic rhinitis occurs more often in males than females during childhood, but this pattern reverses during adolescence [14].

A study of BMI classes (healthy weight, overweight, and obesity) for both allergic rhinitis sufferers and control subjects revealed no statistically significant differences. The BMIs of both male and female subjects were overweight. Although it hasn't been confirmed, there may be a link between obesity and allergic rhinitis in terms of elevated body mass index (BMI) [15]. Numerous consequences of obesity on the immune system may contribute significantly to the rise in allergic diseases [16]. Family history factors play an important influence in allergy disorders, including allergic rhinitis. Parents who have allergic disorders significantly increase their children's risk of developing allergic rhinitis [17]. The current results were 55.5% with hereditary family, and comparable results have been reported in recent study achieved by Rahman et al, they highlighted the significant impact of family history on the prevalence of allergic rhinitis [18]. Regarding education levels there are higher significant differences between control and patients' groups. Certain diseases, such as allergic rhinitis, which causes chronic and distressing symptoms, are linked with poor performance in school [19]. Previous investigations revealed a link between allergic rhinitis and poor school performance [20].

In this study, nonsmokers comprised the vast majority of allergic rhinitis patients. Based to the data, there was no statistically significant difference between patients who nonsmoker and those who smokers. However, the present study aligns with a previous study, which reported that 81.40% have never smoked ordinary cigarettes [21]. However, there is no evidence that smoking increases the prevalence of rhinitis. This could be due to smoking starting later in age. In the current study, duration and severity of symptoms there are higher significant differences with allergic rhinitis. The duration of the disease has a significant effect on how allergic rhinitis develops since it can cause symptoms to intensify and become more severe over time. Additionally, there may be variations in the duration and severity of allergic rhinitis. According to research done in Saudi Arabia, 43% of participants had severe allergic rhinitis [22]. A previous study found that the prevalence of allergic rhinitis increased from 20% to 25% over a nine-year period [23].

The data from current study the onset age had a higher percentage 44.4% in the age range of between 5 and 20 years. The age range of 11 to 49 years is at risk for allergic rhinitis, according to previous study [24]. The total number of WBCs and differentiation cells were greater in allergic rhinitis patients than in the control. Activation of circulating neutrophils can cause mucosal inflammation, with greater neutrophil counts among allergic rhinitis patients [25]. Eosinophils are increased in allergic rhinitis patients, which is comparable with various prior investigations [26][27]. Eosinophils play a crucial role in atopic disease, with higher levels in the blood and tissues of patients with allergic diseases [28]. Most of the patients in our investigation had a significant level of total IgE. A distinct immunoglobulin called IgE is essential to the pathophysiology of both acute and chronic allergic responses [29]. The age group of 28 to 30 years old had the largest peak of total IgE [30].

The current study's main objective was to investigate the association between numerous parameters, including WBC count, IgE, disease duration, and onset of disease in patients with diverse study variables.

The current data, revealed a robust positive correlation between IgE and illness onset. Also, WBC interacts with both lymphocytes and neutrophils, as well as eosinophils with RBC. There is a strong negative association between disease duration and onset. High levels of total IgE are more common in allergy patients compared to normal populations [31]. Elevated levels of total IgE were linked to severe symptoms in patients with chronic allergic rhinitis, suggesting that it may be a predictive factor for allergic rhinitis severity [32]. Prior research on the connection between the NLR and PLR ratios in children with atopic dermatitis [33].

6. Conclusion:

According to the current study, the findings showed that, in comparison to the control group, patients with allergic rhinitis had noticeably higher levels of inflammatory markers. High levels of eosinophils and IgE were indicated of allergic rhinitis, an inflammation of the airways. These linked them to the clinical severity of allergic rhinitis.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interests.

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